

Madagascar electrification plan for 2030, through OnSSET

Madagascar team

Marie Emondine RASOARIMALALA, Ministry of Energy and Hydrocarbons

Heritiana RAZAFINDRAKOTO, ADER

Andriampanarivo RAKOTONDRATSIMBA, ORE

08/05/2025

Keywords

Madagascar, Electrification in Madagascar, OnSSET, LCOE, Data, Technologies of Electricity,

Acknowledgements

This report was produced as a result of our participation in the Energy Modelling Platform for Africa (EMP-A), held from 21 April to 9 May 2025 at the United Nations Economic Commission for Africa (UNECA) in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.

Our heartfelt thanks go to our outstanding trainers, Andreas Sahlberg, Julian Cantor, and Thierry Odou, for their dedication, insightful guidance, and continued support throughout the program.

We would like to acknowledge the organizers of EMP-A, namely: Climate Compatible Growth (CCG), United Nations Economic Commission for Africa (UNECA), World Bank Group, Sustainable Energy for All (SEforALL), Politecnico di Milano, International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), and the World Resources Institute (WRI), whose collective efforts made this platform a rich and valuable learning experience.

Our participation was made possible thanks to the support of the Malagasy Government, through the Ministry of Energy, the Office de Régulation de l'Électricité (ORE), and l'Agence de Développement de l'Électrification Rurale (ADER), whose commitment to capacity building in the energy sector is deeply appreciated.

Participation in the event was supported by Sustainable Energy for All through funding from The Rockefeller Foundation. SEforALL also acknowledges its institutional funders: Austrian Development Cooperation, Ministry for Foreign Affairs of Iceland, People's Postcode Lottery, and the Global Energy Alliance for People and Planet.

This material has been produced with support from the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) programme. CCG is funded by UK aid from the UK government. However, the views expressed herein do not necessarily reflect the UK government's official policies.

Executive Summary

This study focuses on electrification planning for Madagascar using the OnSSET model to explore viable pathways toward universal electricity access by 2030. The goal was to identify a solution that is cost-effective, realistic, and scalable, while ensuring economic and social sustainability.

Based on the M300 framework, four OnSSET scenarios were analyzed. Among them, Scenario 1 emerged as the most viable, combining grid extension, mini-grids, and standalone systems to match the country's diverse needs. The scenario projects 4.64 million new connections, 958 MW of installed capacity, and a required investment of USD 5.59 billion by 2030.

Most new connections would be achieved through the existing grid (667 MW), supplemented by 214 MW from hybrid mini-grids, 66 MW from standalone solar PV, 10 MW from hydro, and 1 MW via grid expansion.

Although the model provides solid guidance, some results may be underestimated due to data limitations. Improving data quality and refining inputs will be key for accurate planning and effective implementation.

1. Introduction

Access to modern energy services remains a fundamental driver of socio-economic development, yet millions in Africa still lack access to electricity and clean cooking solutions. This study focuses on Madagascar, aligning with the government's ambition to achieve 80% electricity access and 50% clean cooking access. These national targets contribute to the broader continental goal of providing sustainable energy access to 300 million people across Africa a mission critical to realizing inclusive growth and climate resilience.

The purpose of this study is to analyze and compare electrification scenarios using the Open Source Spatial Electrification Tool (OnSSET), which enables data-driven, geospatial planning of energy access pathways. The scope includes an evaluation of four distinct scenarios, each reflecting a different strategic prioritization in electrification rollout:

- Scenario 1: Prioritizes areas with the lowest investment cost per capita.
- Scenario 2: Targets the largest population settlements first.
- Scenario 3: Focuses on settlements that are most easily accessible, based on travel time.
- Scenario 4: Emphasizes proximity to main road networks to optimize logistics and grid extension feasibility.

This analysis aims to support national energy planning by identifying electrification strategies that are not only cost-effective but also scalable and practical. The goal is to help accelerate progress toward Madagascar's 2030 energy access targets. By weighing the trade-offs between economic efficiency, equity, and on-the-ground feasibility, the study provides evidence to inform policy and investment decisions that can drive the country toward universal electricity access—aligned with the global “300 million” mission.

2. Methodology

2.1 Modeling Approach and Tool Implemented

This study uses the Open-Source Spatial Electrification Tool (OnSSET), a geospatial least-cost electrification modeling platform developed to support national and regional energy access planning. OnSSET integrates spatial data with techno-economic parameters to determine the most cost-effective electrification options grid extension, mini-grids, or standalone systems for each settlement.

The tool models long-term electrification pathways based on demand projections, infrastructure costs, and geographic constraints, and is particularly well-suited for evaluating various rollout strategies under differing policy priorities.

2.2 Data Sources

To ensure comprehensive and context-specific analysis, the following data were used:

- Demographic and Settlement Data: WorldPop, AfriPop, and national census statistics (latest available).
- Infrastructure Data: Existing High Voltage Lines, Existing Medium Voltage Lines, Madagascar Substation, Existing mini-grid (Jirama Isolated powerplant & Private sector mini-grids); Madagascar Health facilities; Madagascar School data;
- Main roads for road networks and transmission grid; government sources for planned grid expansion.
- Renewable Resource Data: Global solar irradiance and wind speed datasets from Global Solar Atlas and Global Wind Atlas. Hydro data base from IEP (Integrated Energy Plan)
- Travel time
- Nightlights
- Custom demand
- Cost Parameters: ADER cost benchmarks for technology-specific CAPEX/OPEX, fuel prices, and tariff structures.
- Administrative Boundaries: GADM (Global Administrative Areas) for regional delineations within Madagascar.

2.3 Assumptions

To ensure comparability across scenarios, the following core assumptions were applied:

- Planning Horizon: 2023–2030.
- Electrification target rate = 80%
- Demographics and social components:

Start year population	28 000 000
Urban ratio start year	18%
Grid elec ratio start year	32%
Grid urban elec ratio	67%
Grid rural elec ratio	14%
End year population	36 000 000
Urban ratio end year	40%

Number of people per household urban	3,9
Number of people per household rural	4,3

- Population Growth: 2.7% annual growth rate based on national estimates.
- Demand Tiers:

Designation	Tier	kWh/household/year
Residential urban target	4	1 241
Rural target large	3	365
Rural target small	2	73

- Electrification Technologies: Grid, mini-grid (hydro, solar PV-based with battery and diesel backup), and standalone PV systems.
- Electrification approach: On the GEP Explorer, there are currently two options in use.

- ✓ Nationwide Least Cost approach

As we have defined before, the target rate is 80%, we will prioritize grid densification first then selection based on lowest investment cost per capita to choose which clusters to be electrified.

- ✓ Forced grid approach: under 5 km buffer distance and least cost approach outside of the buffer zone

So, we have done = 2 000 usd / household for forced grid intensification.

1. Scenarios and Sensitivity Analysis

To explore how strategic priorities impact electrification outcomes, four scenarios were developed based on different rollout criteria:

- ✓ Scenario 1: based on the lowest investment cost per capita
- ✓ Scenario 2: based on the largest settlements first
- ✓ Scenario 3: based on the most easily reached settlements, based on travel time
- ✓ Scenario 4: based on the lowest distance to main roads

These methodological steps enable a rigorous comparison of spatially optimized electrification pathways that align with Madagascar's national targets and broader continental access goals.

3. Results

- Charts and Graphs

✓ Scenario 1: based on the lowest investment cost per capita

Item	Population 2030	New Connections 2030	Capacity 2030 (MW)	Investment 2030 (million USD)
Existing grid	16 577 628	1 885 456	667	2 579
Grid Extension	18 961	4 861	1	7
SHS	6 343 363	1 627 450	66	1 584
PV Hybrid Mini-Grid	5 305 280	1 065 864	214	1 327
Wind Hybrid Mini-Grid	-	-	-	-
Hydro Mini Grid	225 049	57 702	10	99
Unelectrified	7 200 139	-	-	-
Total	35 670 422	4 641 333	958	5 597

Item	Population 2030	New Connections 2030	Capacity 2030 (MW)	Investment 2030 (million USD)
Existing grid	16 577 628	1 885 456	667	2 579
Grid Extension	18 961	4 861	1	7
SHS	6 343 363	1 627 450	66	1 584
PV Hybrid Mini-Grid	5 305 280	1 065 864	214	1 327
Wind Hybrid Mini-Grid	-	-	-	-
Hydro Mini Grid	225 049	57 702	10	99
Unelectrified	7 200 139	-	-	-
Total	35 670 422	4 641 333	958	5 597

✓ Scenario 2: based on the largest settlements first

Item	Population 2030	New Connections 2030	Capacity 2030 (MW)	Investment 2030 (million USD)
Existing grid	16 577 628	1 885 456	667	2 579
Grid Extension	213 570	54 759	6	121
SHS	1 846 298	470 859	108	4 306
PV Hybrid Mini-Grid	9 611 427	2 137 242	516	3 251
Wind Hybrid Mini-Grid	-	-	-	-
Hydro Mini Grid	225 049	57 702	10	99
Unelectrified	7 200 060	-	-	-
Total	35 674 034	4 606 018	1 306	10 356

✓ Scenario 3: based on the most easily reached settlements, based on travel time

Item	Population 2030	New Connections 2030	Capacity 2030 (MW)	Investment 2030 (million USD)
Existing grid	16 577 628	1 885 456	667	2 579
Grid Extension	273 214	70 069	7	163
SHS	5 771 076	1 478 314	145	5 122
PV Hybrid Mini-Grid	5 622 621	1 134 444	275	1 695
Wind Hybrid Mini-Grid	-	-	-	-
Hydro Mini Grid	225 049	57 702	10	99
Unelectrified	7 200 065	-	-	-
Total	35 669 654	4 625 985	1 105	9 659

✓ Scenario 4: based on the lowest distance to main roads

Item	Population 2030	New Connections 2030	Capacity 2030 (MW)	Investment 2030 (million USD)
Existing grid	16 577 628	1 885 456	667	2 579
Grid Extension	174 798	44 830	5	111
SHS	4 956 704	1 269 818	120	4 238
PV Hybrid Mini-Grid	6 537 236	1 352 367	375	2 152
Wind Hybrid Mini-Grid	-	-	-	-
Hydro Mini Grid	225 049	57 702	10	99
Unelectrified	7 200 664	-	-	-
Total	35 672 080	4 610 173	1 177	9 180

a. Main findings of results

b. Differences between scenarios

To interpret the results and derive the most realistic scenario, we used three indicators:

Cost_per_connection : Which is the Average amount invested to connect a household

$$\text{Cost per connection} = \frac{\text{Investment2030 (million USD)} \times 1,000,000}{\text{NewConnections2030}}$$

Capacity_per_person : Which is the Average power available per inhabitant.

$$\text{Capacity per person} = \frac{\text{Capacity2030 (MW)} \times 1,000,000}{\text{Population2030}}$$

Investment_per_person : Which is the Average amount invested for each inhabitant (whether connected or not)

$$\text{Investment per person} = \frac{\text{Investment}_{2030} \text{ (million USD)} \times 1,000,000}{\text{Population}_{2030}}$$

And we have the table below

Criteria	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario3	Scenario 4
Total cost (USD millions)	5 597	10 356	9 659	9 180
Cost per connection (USD)	1 206	2 248	2 088	1 991
Capacity per person (W)	26,86	36,62	30,97	33,01
Invest. per capita (USD)	157	290	271	257

The result is **Scenario 1** is the most realistic if we are looking for a strong economic compromise, with :

- 1.1. The lowest total cost per connection
- 1.2. A reasonable investment per inhabitant
- 1.3. Acceptable capacity per person (even if slightly lower than the others)

Scenarios 2 to 4 offer better technical performance (more capacity per inhabitant), but at a much higher cost.

4. Discussion

The results provide valuable insights for national electrification planning. Scenario 1 offers a balanced approach with the lowest overall investment, reasonable cost per connection, and feasible implementation strategies. Although other scenarios offer higher capacity per person, their cost implications may pose funding and logistical challenges.

Hydropower, given Madagascar's natural potential, should be prioritized in future planning. Additional analysis could explore mixed hydro-PV solutions to maximize resource availability. Furthermore, integrating productive use considerations—agriculture, small enterprises—into demand projections would improve realism.

Limitations include the simplification of demand, incomplete infrastructure data, and static assumptions. A dynamic planning model could consider population migration, policy changes, and infrastructure development.

Future research could enhance the model through detailed load profiles, real CAPEX/OPEX benchmarks, and regional differentiation. Furthermore, ONSSET should be integrated into national planning cycles and training institutions to build long-term capacity in spatial electrification modeling.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrates the usefulness of the OnSSET model for planning Madagascar's path toward universal electricity access by 2030. By comparing four electrification scenarios, the analysis identified Scenario 1 as the most viable option, balancing cost, scalability, and service quality. It emphasizes grid densification supported by mini-grids and standalone systems. Refining input data, considering environmental implications, and enhancing model flexibility are key areas for improvement. Institutionalizing OnSSET into national energy planning and training will further improve decision-making for inclusive and sustainable electrification.

References

#	Dataset	Links
1	Administrative boundaries	https://geodata.ucdavis.edu/gadm/gadm4.1/gpkg/gadm41_MDG.gpkg
2	Medium-voltage lines (Existing)	https://datacatalog.worldbank.org/search/dataset/0039596/Madagascar-Electricity-Transmission-Network
3	Medium-voltage lines (Planned)	https://datacatalog.worldbank.org/search/dataset/0039596/Madagascar-Electricity-Transmission-Network
4	Distribution transformers (MV/LV)	https://energydata.info/dataset/madagascar-substations-2015
5	Substations	https://energydata.info/dataset/madagascar-substations-2015
6	High-voltage lines (Existing)	https://datacatalog.worldbank.org/search/dataset/0039596/Madagascar-Electricity-Transmission-Network
7	High-voltage lines (Planned)	https://datacatalog.worldbank.org/search/dataset/0039596/Madagascar-Electricity-Transmission-Network
8	Road network *	https://download.geofabrik.de/africa.html
9	Settlement clusters	PopClusters - Mendeley Data
10	Global Horizontal Irradiation (GHI)	https://api.globalsolaratlas.info/download/Madagascar/Madagascar_GHI_poster-map_800x1200mm-300dpi_v20191017.tif
11	Small scale hydropower sites *	
12	Wind velocity (m/s)	Global Wind Atlas
13	Travel time (min) *	https://data.malariaatlas.org/
14	Night-time lights *	https://eogdata.mines.edu/products/vnl/
15	Existing mini-grid locations	https://app.datafraym.io/wiki/38/plugin/attachments/download/285/
16	Custom demand layer (if bottom-up approach is included)	https://energydata.info/dataset/madagascar-global-electrification-platform-gep**
17	Location of Health Facilities (if social uses are included)	https://app.datafraym.io/wiki/madagascar-iep-tool-metadata/#wiki-toc-modele-de-chaine-du-froid-cold-chain-model https://data.humdata.org/dataset/madagascar-healthsites
18	Location of Education Institutions (if social uses are included)	https://app.datafraym.io/wiki/madagascar-iep-tool-metadata/#wiki-toc-modele-de-chaine-du-froid-cold-chain-model https://data.humdata.org/dataset/world-bank-education-indicators-for-madagascar

Appendices

Appendix A: Scenario comparison table

Scenario	Item	Population 2030	New Connections 2030	Capacity 2030 (MW)	Investment 2030 (million USD)
1	Existing grid	16 577 628	1 885 456	667	2 579
	Grid Extension	18 961	4 861	1	7
	SHS	6 343 363	1 627 450	66	1 584
	PV Hybrid Mini-Grid	5 305 280	1 065 864	214	1 327
	Wind Hybrid Mini-Grid	-	-	-	-
	Hydro Mini Grid	225 049	57 702	10	99
	Unelectrified	7 200 139	-	-	-
	Total	35 670 422	4 641 333	958	5 597
2	Existing grid	16 577 628	1 885 456	667	2 579
	Grid Extension	213 570	54 759	6	121
	SHS	1 846 298	470 859	108	4 306
	PV Hybrid Mini-Grid	9 611 427	2 137 242	516	3 251
	Wind Hybrid Mini-Grid	-	-	-	-
	Hydro Mini Grid	225 049	57 702	10	99
	Unelectrified	7 200 060	-	-	-
	Total	35 674 034	4 606 018	1 306	10 356
3	Existing grid	16 577 628	1 885 456	667	2 579
	Grid Extension	273 214	70 069	7	163
	SHS	5 771 076	1 478 314	145	5 122
	PV Hybrid Mini-Grid	5 622 621	1 134 444	275	1 695
	Wind Hybrid Mini-Grid	-	-	-	-
	Hydro Mini Grid	225 049	57 702	10	99
	Unelectrified	7 200 065	-	-	-
	Total	35 669 654	4 625 985	1 105	9 659
4	Existing grid	16 577 628	1 885 456	667	2 579
	Grid Extension	174 798	44 830	5	111
	SHS	4 956 704	1 269 818	120	4 238
	PV Hybrid Mini-Grid	6 537 236	1 352 367	375	2 152
	Wind Hybrid Mini-Grid	-	-	-	-
	Hydro Mini Grid	225 049	57 702	10	99
	Unelectrified	7 200 664	-	-	-
	Total	35 672 080	4 610 173	1 177	9 180

Appendix B: Key OnSSET model assumptions

Commun Assumption to all scenario

- Start year: 2023 ; End year: 2030
- Urban target tier : 4
- Rural target tier large: 3
- Rural target tier small: 2
- Hydro prioritisation distance : 5 km
- Min number of household for mini grid to be considered : 400
- Min distance from existing MV lines for mini-grids to be considered as option: 10 km

Appendix C: Input data sources and parameters

